

HumanTech News | June 2025
HumanTech Highlights

Dear community,

Now that [HumanTech](#) has officially come to an end, we want to celebrate the incredible journey we've shared over the past three years — and thank our [HumanTech team](#), whose work made it all possible!

Together, we've created a wide range of human-centred technologies aimed at making construction safer, smarter, and more sustainable. From autonomous robotics and scan-to-BIM pipelines to wearables for physically demanding tasks, AI-powered bridge inspections, and XR safety monitoring tools — we've piloted our technologies across five real-world construction sites across Europe. [As our Project Coordinator, Jason Rambach, puts it](#), "It's been impressive to witness how hard work allowed us to progress from individual research results and components [...] to five fully integrated [HumanTech Pilots](#) in different locations all over Europe and even beyond."

To everyone who contributed to this shared effort: THANK YOU! ❤️

While the project may be ending, its results — from the technologies we've developed to the open resources we've shared and the partnerships we've built —

will continue to shape a new vision for the construction sector, one that puts workers at the centre of digital transformation and drives innovation, for years to come.

Explore our final publication to learn more about our solutions:

Explore HumanTech's most impactful outcomes

Don't miss out! Follow us on our social channels and [subscribe to this newsletter](#) to stay updated.

Now, let's dive into our pilot projects, training materials, resources, publications, and Tech4EUconstruction cluster updates. Enjoy!

HumanTech Pilots

Over the past months, we've focused on integrating, testing, and validating our technologies through collaborative **demo sessions**. We've also gathered user feedback to help refine our solutions — each designed to address a specific challenge faced by the EU construction sector today.

In our [HumanTech Pilots articles](#) and [videos](#), the partners behind each pilot explain how these technologies benefit the construction industry and the professionals working in it.

Robotic application of mastic in concrete expansion joints

[Watch the video](#)

BIMxD-based autonomous robotic task planning

[Watch the video](#)

Robotics and wearables for collaborative bricklaying

[Watch the video](#)

Bridge inspection and monitoring

Watch the video

Dynamic semantic digital twin

Watch the video

These pilots bring together expertise from across our partners and showcase how human-centred innovation can transform the construction industry — making it safer, more efficient, attractive and accessible to a new generation of workers.

[Watch all our pilot videos](#) to see HumanTech solutions in action!

HumanTech Pilots

Human-centred technologies
contributing to a safer, more efficient,
and technology-driven construction.

humantech

Funded by
the European Union

HumanTech Training Materials

As part of our commitment to knowledge-sharing, we've developed **10 micro-learning units** (MLUs) to support upskilling and promote the adoption of digital technologies across the construction sector. These modules cover key areas where digitalisation can bring the most value for workers, such as BIM fundamentals, green technology, and robotics.

[Explore, use, and share our training materials](#), and watch our colleague [Martin Breen's video](#) introducing them.

HumanTech Training Materials

10 micro-learning units (MLUs)
to bring cutting-edge construction technology
into the classroom

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Funded by
the European Union

Additional resources and scientific publications

Research & Publications

We've published a wide range of [scientific papers](#) in leading conferences and journals — including CVPR, ICCV, and ISARC. To date, six additional publications have already been accepted, with eight more currently under review. Our work has also been recognised with multiple **awards**, highlighting the impact of our research.

Deliverables & Open Source Tools

We've made available our **latest public deliverables** — detailed reports documenting the progress and outcomes of our work — along with [open-source tools](#), including source code repositories and datasets linked to many of our scientific publications.

The latest in our Tech4EUconstruction cluster

Collaboration across the eight EU-funded projects in the [Tech4EUconstruction cluster](#) has continued through joint campaigns and coordinated activities, strengthening our collective impact and connecting with a broader community around innovation in construction.

Recently, we launched a social media campaign to promote a joint [questionnaire on Gender inclusion in the construction sector](#) and joined forces in several events, such as the 2025 editions of the [European Robotics Forum 2025](#) — with a workshop on applying robotics in efficient and sustainable construction and deconstruction — and [Hannover Messe](#), one of the world's biggest industrial tech fairs, where we promoted our work through brochures, videos, and interactive displays.

Representatives from BEEYONDERS, RoBétArmé, DISCOVER and HumanTech at the [European Robotics Forum \(ERF\) 2025](#).

To finish, one last recommendation

Smarter. Safer. Greener.

Shaping the future of construction with innovative, human-centred technologies for a safer, smarter, and more sustainable industry.

[Explore our latest publication to learn more about our solutions,](#)
designed to make construction safer,
boost efficiency, and improve
working conditions throughout the
entire construction process.

This journey wouldn't have been possible without the dedication of our partners and community. Thank you for helping shape the future of construction!

Thanks for reading,
The HumanTech Team

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